

Digital Transformation Moving away from legacy software to system of interaction

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Technology is changing at fast speed. New systems are required for new devices. In this case migration from current software platform to new digital services becomes often intimidating.

There are millions of software systems used around the world to make the life easy. Many among these software's are so old-school that they seem to end their lifespan due to its out dated functionalities.

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Overloaded with interfaces and technology platforms that are a decade or two ago, these tools are mostly used on the desktops only, occupying a historical code which are irreplaceable yet required in daily work.

The users are too frustrated to cope with such systems. However, as a data source, they have no other option other than using these intelligence systems. It includes tracking and workflow solutions, process management and similar such software tools which are quite ancient. Such ancient methods are likely to end in near future. The use of software depends upon the existence of providers.

Why it is taking time to adopt the change?

This software systems comes up with years of maintenance work and hence generate continuous revenue to the service providers. Once the contract is signed it remains for years with the framed guidelines and specifications. A huge risk is involved while intending for a change. Challenges may arise which can take a long time to reach its solutions and meanwhile the competitors would move ahead in the market. Therefore, a thought to step back and stay with legacy systems seems wise under such consequences.

At buyer's end – again it's the same concern. Once the software system gets installed in thousands of users, they expect consistent user experience. Changing any single thing can lead to loss of buyers or their dislike towards using the system. Organization's from provider as well as buyer side have entered into panic zone because of these risks associated with change.

The signs of these legacy software systems reaching to its rot are-

- Threat of the loss of a big customer to a provider
- Increasing competitive processes to acquire new customers
- Strong downward pressure on price
- Shorter contract extensions rather than full-term renewals

Gradually, a change is taking place, with the increasing awareness among buyers. They are moving towards the providers who are quick and have potential to keep up the pace with the current technologies.

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From legacy system to system of interaction

Digital services are leading the future of every software eco system. They have already outdated many ancient leading software. With this the customers' expectation are increased and they no longer want the old version of such legacy systems. They want adaptable services that are quick to understand and easy to manage offering them the value additions.

Realizing the change and adapting the system which is beneficial for future is the ultimate success. As this connects with user and not only buyers. It will definitely open up entire new avenues for [product engineering services](#).

As the provider of Digital services to legacy software systems should take care about

- inherently free of device constraints
- have interfaces that reflect any device, place and user
- monetized flexibly

Opportunity is all in your hands, as the provider of a digital service. Build stronger and deeper relationships with customer through genuine insight into their usage.

At Gateway TechnoLabs, we provide services that span the entire product lifecycle from developing concepts to ensuring long-term sustainable competitive advantages for your software products with the right type of requirement specifications, design, development, testing and deployments. Our software development life cycle starts with conceptualization, which is the most critical phase for determining product vision and roadmap, the delivery phase where you are able to introduce right product in the market, and further to ensure it is geared for long-term performance.

Our consultants are here to guide the best path for your legacy systems. Get in touch with us to discover the possibilities.

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